

IMPROVING INSTRUMENTS OF FINANCIAL POLICY OF THE STATE

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Annotation. The article examines the main issues of improving the instruments of the state's financial policy and issues of increasing the rationality of the financial activities of states, examines various aspects of the development of the financial policy of countries and possible methods and ways of its development and improvement.

Key words. Financial policy, financial resources, economic growth, state financial policy instruments, monetary policy, tax (fiscal) policy, investment policy, budget regulation.

The issues of increasing the rationality of the financial activities of states and improving financial policy instruments are classified as permanent, because the need to evaluate and improve its effectiveness has always been, is and will be important. Despite the permanent absolute growth, various options for obtaining, distributing and redistributing financial resources and, at the same time, their objective limitations, consistently contribute only to the deterioration and aggravation of the problem. Accordingly, this existing contradiction is, in our opinion, the main driving force in improving financial policy instruments.¹⁶

At its core, the financial policy of the state is a system of decisions that are aimed at managing public finances and regulating economic processes. Its main goal is to ensure and achieve sustainable economic development, maintain financial stability and social protection of the population. When implementing financial policy, the main and important tools are tax (fiscal) policy, expenditure policy, public debt management, monetary policy and investment policy.

Main aspects of the state's financial policy are:

- Budget development and its approval.
- Tax regulation:

¹⁶ <https://economy-lib.com/finansovaya-politika-gosudarstva-metodologiya-otsenki-i-povysheniya-rezultativnosti>

- Public debt management:
- Regulation of money circulation.
- Implementation of investment policy to stimulate economic growth, etc.

Stimulating the influx and actively attracting foreign direct investment in strategically important sectors can contribute to the expansion of production, technological renewal and the creation of new jobs.

The main issues of financial policy at the present stage are achieving a balance between state revenues and expenses, ensuring the stability of the national currency, controlling inflation and ensuring the well-being of citizens. It also aims to solve social problems, such as ensuring access to healthcare, education and social protection.¹⁷

The need to improve the state's financial policy instruments is explained by the relevance of ensuring sustainable economic development, stable economic growth and effective management of public finances. Achieving this goal requires the development and implementation of modern and adaptive tools that help optimize income, manage public debt, and stimulate economic growth and social stability.

An important aspect in increasing the efficiency of the financial system is fiscal policy; it plays a significant role in the financial policy of the state. The need to improve tax (fiscal) policy includes ensuring effective management of government revenues and expenditures in order to stimulate economic growth, ensure financial sustainability, social justice and balanced development of regions. Therefore, it is necessary to develop and implement modern mechanisms of fiscal regulation, increase tax efficiency, optimize government spending and ensure transparency of fiscal activities in order to increase the competitiveness of the economy and improve the quality of life of citizens.

In recent years, the tax policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan has gone through and continues to go through changes and stages of active reforms and modernization in order to stimulate financial and economic development and improve the investment climate in the country. Key aspects of the tax policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan are the tax structure, ongoing fiscal reforms, digitalization of tax administration, support for small and medium-sized businesses, and international tax cooperation. Uzbekistan has both direct and indirect taxes. Major direct taxes include:

¹⁷ <https://www.bibliofond.ru/view.aspx?id=904649>

Pic.1. The list of direct taxes of the Republic of Uzbekistan¹⁸

Recent years have been characterized by major tax reforms, which are aimed at simplifying tax administration, reducing tax rates and expanding the tax base. The reforms are also aimed at reducing economic modernization.

An important step in the reform is the review and amendment of VAT rates and the expansion of the list of goods and services to which this tax does not apply, which helps to stimulate certain sectors of the economy. Tax reforms in Uzbekistan are aimed at creating a more attractive tax system for potential foreign investors by reducing the tax burden on enterprises. This includes reducing income tax rates for certain categories of entrepreneurs.

In the past few years, many significant changes have taken place in the field of financial policy and the financial system of the Republic.:

— one of the main steps towards improving financial policy is to improve financial transparency, that is, the formation of a consolidated budget that combines the state budget, budgets of state trust funds (the list is approved by a decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan), as well as funds from the Fund for Reconstruction and Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan without taking into account transfers between them, which since 2020 has been put into effect by the annual Law “On the State Budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan” (before that - by the

¹⁸ https://nrm.uz/products?folder=179186_vidy_nalogov&products=1_vse_zakonodatelstvo_uzbekistana

annual presidential decree “On macroeconomic indicators and parameters of the state budget”);

— in order to more fully account and reflect the budget of the public administration sector and achieve compliance with international standards, a general fiscal balance is being formed from 2020, including the balance of the consolidated budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan and expenses for the implementation of state programs through external debt covered from the state budget;

— a maximum value of sovereign debt has been established (2019-2021 - 50% of GDP, 2022-2024 - 60% of GDP).¹⁹ To achieve compliance with international standards, from 2020, expenses for repaying public debt (principal debt) are not included in state budget expenses. Repayment of the principal amount of debt is reflected in the sources of financing the budget deficit;

— there are two-tier budget and one-tier tax systems.²⁰

And also, in connection with the latest reforms in the field of public finance, according to the International Monetary Fund (IMF), Uzbekistan’s GDP in 2023 reached 1.07 quadrillion soums compared to the level of 2022 and reached 6%. The IMF forecasts GDP growth of around 5.5-6% until 2025.²¹

Public finances	(as a percentage % of GDP)				
	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Real GDP growth rate (percentage change)	7.4	5.7	6.0	5.4	5.5
Nominal GDP (trillion soums)	738	897	1,067	1,267	1,505
Consolidated budget revenues	27.7	32.0	30.1	30.5	30.6
Expenditures of the consolidated budget	33.2	36.0	35.6	34.5	33.6
Balance of the consolidated budget	-5.5	-4.0	-5.5	-4.0	-3.0

¹⁹ Budget for citizens. URL: <https://openbudget.uz/ru/publicbudget>; Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan, ON THE STATE BUDGET OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN FOR 2022. from 30.12.2021 r. № LRU-742

²⁰ Sirojiddinova Z.Kh. Public finance system: management reform, areas of improvement in the Republic of Uzbekistan // Financial Journal. 2023. T. 15. № 3. C. 122–142. <https://doi.org/10.31107/2075-1990-2023-3-122-142>.

²¹ <https://www.cer.uz/en/post/publication/uzbekistan-v-ekonomiceskoj-transformacii>

Loans for reforms	1.5	-0.1	1.0	0.7	0.6
Overall budget balance 2/	-6.0	-4.0	-5.5	-4.0	-3.0
State debt	35.3	33.9	36.3	35.7	34.7

«The Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan plans to reduce the budget deficit to 4 percent of GDP in 2024 and to 3 percent of GDP in 2025». ²² This broad fiscal consolidation is necessary to maintain the sustainability of public finances and contain inflation pressures in the near term, but it also needs to protect vulnerable populations and improve economic performance over the medium term. Consolidation is planned to be underpinned by pro-growth policies, such as reducing untargeted energy subsidies while maintaining assistance to vulnerable people, better targeting of social and safety net spending, and reducing directed lending. The authorities should be prepared to take additional measures to achieve budget deficit targets if risks associated with budget revenues and/or expenditures materialize. Existing opportunities to expand the tax base, further modernize the tax system, improve spending efficiency, strengthen core budget processes, unify the public investment process, and better manage fiscal risks will support the authorities' continued fiscal efforts. Continuous development of human resource capacity in areas such as tax policy, revenue administration and public financial management has enabled the authorities to implement an effective value added tax system and make significant progress in developing a budget strategy and budget risk report to improve the budget management system, as well as monitoring and managing fiscal risks. It is necessary to continue work in these areas. To avoid risks associated with PPPs, the mission recommends setting a guarantee ceiling for PPP projects in accordance with the public debt law, taking into account the results of the ongoing inventory.

Modern challenges in the world and the changing economic environment suggest the need to improve the instruments of the state's financial policy. To achieve the above goals, it is necessary to actively participate in the development and implementation of policies that promote private sector development, improve

²² "Uzbekistan: Final Mission Statement from the 2024 Article IV Consultation" - IMF - <https://www.imf.org/ru/News/Articles/2024/05/14/mcs-uzbekistan-staff-concluding-statement-of-the-2024-article-iv-mission>

infrastructure, increase productivity, support innovation and create an enabling business environment.

Attention should also be paid to the development of financial literacy, monetary regulation and investment policy in order to maintain macroeconomic stability and the sustainability of the financial system.

In conclusion, it is important to note that improving the government's financial policy requires a balanced approach to managing finances, stimulating economic growth and ensuring financial stability in the long term.

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